

Technology Assessment and Insertion for The Defense Information Systems Network (DISN)

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Abstract

The DISN will evolve with new capabilities being added based on requirements and availability of technologies. The identification and transition of technologies from the research and development communities, including service laboratories, industry, and academia, to the acquisition managers requires an approved process that defines the methodology and assigns responsibilities. The main purpose of this paper is to present and discuss the strategy for technology insertion into DISN. In order to accomplish this, a management process for technology insertion has been defined which addresses three key issues to insure that the programmatic/cost and technical risks are minimized. The principal driver for technology insertion is the identification of candidate technologies that are in concert with the approved DISN architecture which have the potential to enhance the capabilities of the DISN in meeting the needs of the warfighters/customers in a cost effective way.

1.0 Introduction

The Department of Defense recognizes that information is one of the most important assets in conducting modern warfare. Using information effectively requires developing an information system that will encompass all of DoD-one that will allow users throughout the organization to access, manipulate, move, and manage information to best support their functions. Moreover, America's economic performance and international influence rest, in large part, on its technology base. A 21st century infrastructure program in a new framework for U. S. technology has been presented to develop and quickly utilize new technologies [1].

There is a shift from a global Soviet threat to a wide range of potential threats with a regional focus and a reduced forward presence supporting flexible response. The implications for information systems support for command and control include:

streamlining and consolidation (joint and national resources vs. Service unique); interoperability, modularity, flexibility, for rapid deployment to areas where no C3 infrastructure exists and greater reliance on commercial systems that may revise the approach to risk management. The information structure supporting the defense mission [i.e. the Defense Information Infrastructure (DII)] must provide an end-to-end information support capability encompassing collection, generation, storage, display and dissemination of information department wide.

2.0 DISA Roles and Responsibilities

There are a multitude of R&D efforts going on among the Services and Agencies that are somewhat independent. What is needed is a partnership and/or alliance among the government Agencies R&D centers and commercial R&D centers. This will help bring the related efforts together and expedite the insertion of technology into the Defense Wide information Systems environment. There are numerous examples. One is the DDRE Advanced Technology Demonstrations (ATD) efforts. DDRE has come up with 7 Science and Technology thrusts one of which is Global Surveillance and Communications(GSC). GSC has under it three panels in which we at DISA are participating and are making contributions: Communications, Command & Control, and Sensors. There are other activities as well such as our C3 Systems Engineering Conference, our testbed activities, our alliances with other organizations like ARPA in the TWBnet, and our cosponsorship of the Gigabit conference with ARPA and NSA that are helping position DISA as a leader in expediting the insertion of technology into the DoD [2].

DISA will work closely with the industrial R&D sector through alliance with ARPA in the "Technology Reinvestment Project (TRP)" and others to leverage on the development of "Dual-Use" technology. DISA developed a strategy for technology insertion. Considering that DISA will be

the primary consumer of the resulting Information System technology and responsible for inserting it into the Defense Information Infrastructure, DISA actively participates in the R&D community influencing the direction of research and insuring a smooth transition.

DISA would have the following R&D role:

DISA will play the principal role in inserting new technology in the Defense Information System Network (DISN). Therefore it must have a key role in defining DoD needs for R&D in Information Systems technology in order to improve productivity, support functional processes, and enhance the ability of warfighters to flexibly deploy and sustain forces throughout the world. In conjunction with the DoD R&D community (ARPA, the Service Labs, etc.), DISA will be the focal point for identifying technological opportunities (sometimes called Advanced Technology Demonstrations (ATD)) in specific areas to impact future DoD Information System needs and expedite and accelerate the transition of emerging technologies into DoD information systems.

2.1 Architectural Framework

A key characteristic of DISN is that its future architecture will not differ in any substantial way from the generic architecture of all information systems. This allows the DoD to leverage on commercial systems technologies. An information system is made "unique" when its mission specific applications are implemented. But the architecture remains general by providing the structure that permits military users to exchange and process critical time sensitive warning and intelligence information in multiple forms (e.g. voice, data, imagery, etc.). The DII architecture provides for evolvability and interoperability [3].

2.2 Classes of services provided by the DISN

The following classes of services will be provided by the DISN [4]:

- Information management services. These services provide the following:
- Support the storage, control, distribution, management, and allocation of both simple data such as text and numeric information

and complex items such as charts, maps, images, and multimedia objects

- An integrated network management scheme that allows integrated control of network resources at both network and user levels and an automated maintenance system that allows integrated, automated control of information system resources at both the network and user levels.
- Network services that consist of the transmission and interface standards that support the physical and logical communications (the information transfer functions).
- User interface services that provide the visual and functional interaction with the user (e.g. the graphical user interface (GUI))
- Operating systems services that manage the hardware and software resources and all the software interfaces including the distribution and execution of application programs.
- Security services that provide for the privacy, protection, and integrity of complete information base and network and computing assets.
- Programming services that affect the development and execution of application programs.
- Information exchange standards that allow the transfer of all forms of information (e.g. voice, data, imagery, video) that preserves their form, content and appearance.

3.0 THE EMERGING TECHNOLOGY INSERTION PROCESS

The Emerging Technology Insertion Process is shown in Figure 1. The process of identifying candidate technologies, validating their proper application within the DISN, and their implementation into the DII as DISA provided services (e.g. DISN, CIM) is explained in subsequent paragraphs.

Figure 1. Emerging Technology Insertion Process

3.1 The Information Technology Users Role

The user of information technology (e.g. Warfighter, Command and Control implementer and operator, CIM business user, etc.) is central to the technology insertion process. From the technology assessment, through demonstrations and testing, to the final operational service, the user's requirements are the driving force which determines the application of the emerging technology. This participation will involve the using activity in all phases of the process, especially as relates to requirements validation, utility demonstrations and system testing.

3.2 The Selection of Advanced and Emerging Technologies

Candidate technologies for insertion into the service base of the DISA will be identified by the Technology Leaders Group functioning within the Center for Engineering (CFE). This group will accomplish the identification of candidate technologies in generic technology areas such as networking, network management, security, distributed operating systems, etc., through a variety of means described below. Once the candidate technologies are identified, an individual and separate report (an on line database) will be maintained by the CFE that summarizes the status and issues relating to that technology. This database, kept current by the CFE, contains data such as the technology description, implementation status, current activities and analysis and recommendations. A key part of the summary is the recommendations section that

recommends specific actions to be take such as technology demonstrations, pilot service, further R&D and testing, standards development, etc. Based on this a decision will be made whether or not to seek funding from DISA resources.

3.3 Demonstrations

Demonstrations can encompass a wide variety of expositions of technology. Demonstrations will be considered to be the exposition of any technology which provide an opportunity to observe its operational and performance characteristics. They can be conducted at any location, by DISA, other government agencies, or industry. This concept of operations has been conceived to provide the framework for the derivation of performance and operability information from the greatest number of sources. However, the primary focus of this document is on DISA orchestrated demonstrations, conducted under the auspices of the Emerging Technology Base.

All types of demonstrations are implemented to expose users to technology before it is generally available in the market place, and to provide users with the opportunity to develop visions of how to apply the technology. This vision can then be translated into requirements which apply to the specific application of the technology within the DISA service base. User vision and the validation of requirements can also influence vendors of COTS

products as they contemplate the inclusion of various optional features.

The purpose of demonstrations is to provide the basis for further development of the technology aimed at the implementation of a Pilot Service. In order to provide this basis several key actions will accompany the conduct of the demonstration. The first is the performance testing of the products or technologies. This will contribute to the second task of determining and validating user requirements. By involving users in the demonstrations, feedback can be obtained on the effectiveness of the technology from the users view.

Perhaps the most important aspect of the involvement of users in the demonstration process is the validation of their requirements. In conjunction with the operation of demonstration services the users will be invited to participate in the use of the systems to define as precisely as possible their requirements and how the new technology may satisfy their present and projected needs.

Decision Point 1. The first major milestone in the process is the decision to allocate resources to the implementation of a Pilot Service. A demonstration report will be prepared by the Emerging Technology Leaders Group, and presented to the DISA management who will approve or deny the initiation of a Pilot Service. From this point forward in the process this determination will guide the types of engineering development and integration, program planning, and level and formality of testing associated with the product or technology insertion.

3.4 Pilot Services

Once a successful demonstration of candidate technology has occurred and a decision has been made to proceed with the development of the technology a Pilot Service will be constructed by the Program manager (PM). This step in the Emerging Technology Insertion Process will enable a small community of users to receive the benefits of use of the emerging technology. These services may be implemented with proprietary solutions and may be difficult/costly to expand to the community at large. Tradeoffs would have to be made relative to whether or not we should delay implementation pending the development of standards for the provides service. The experience with the capability or service would enable DISA to more thoroughly understand the user requirements and plan for full implementation.

Additionally this is the point in the process which mandates heavy user involvement. User involvement must be undertaken with the idea that risks are inherent in a service of this nature, and that one of their major roles in the process is to constructively evaluate the service in that environment.

Decision Point 2. The second major milestone in the process is the determination of whether resources will be allocated to the implementation of an initial operational service. A Pilot Service report will be prepared and presented to the management of DISA who will approve or disapprove the initiation of initial service.

3.5 Initial Operational Services

The establishment of an initial service is the first real proof of operational compatibility between the emerging technology and currently operating systems. Once a Decision Point 2 decision has been reached to begin implementation and installation of the initial operational service, steps will normally be taken to convert the Pilot Service into an operational service.

The purpose of the establishment of Initial Operational Services is to begin the expansion of the emerging technology within the DISA service base. As the initial service is developed several actions will normally occur. Performance testing of the technology will be continued, and focused more specifically when possible. Next, engineering development of the technology will occur, aimed at preparing for implementation of the capabilities on a much broader scale. Integrated logistical planning and activities will continue on a much greater scale than before, and several specific testing activities will occur. These include an operational test aimed at determining that the fielded systems or services meet user requirements and expectations. This operational test will be expanded to address such items as reliability, availability, and maintainability, logistical support, and user related measures of performance.

Decision Point 3. The third and final milestone of the process is the determination of whether resources will be allocated to the implementation of the service on a broad scale. An Initial Operational Service Report will be prepared and presented to the DISA management by the Emerging Technology Leaders Group for approval or disapproval of the service.

3.6 Final Operational Services

After a decision to proceed from Decision Point 3 has been made, development of the Final Operational Service will begin. Virtually all development and testing activities will have been completed at this point in the insertion process. The program office or group assigned the task of implementing the initial service will draw upon these activities to proliferate the technology. Some special purpose development and testing may be expected to occur during proliferation of the services.

3.7 Engineering Development

Engineering development encompasses a number of tasks related to the establishment of the Pilot Service, the initial operational service, and ultimately the final operational service. It includes the development of interface specifications, the information system architecture and topology, interoperation with current services, the development of extensions to the standards where necessary, and a variety of related tasks.

Building on the experience in the providing of prototype services, DISA will develop methods to satisfy the user community. This would include the development/selection of standards and as a last resort, the development of unique system specifications and equipment required to satisfy the requirements of the warfighter. This enables a thorough examination of the technology prior to specifying it as part of the DII baseline.

3.8 Formal Testing and Evaluation

The testing of advanced and emerging technologies is critical for meeting one of the primary objectives of the program, that of testing all technologies in simulated and real environments before their proliferation in the DISA service base. The testing program should follow a logical progression from performance testing of early prototypes through complete operational tests where applicable.

4.0 Summary

This paper focuses on the process of technology assessment and insertion for DISN. This

work was useful to synthesize different views upon this very critical activity and constitutes a good basis for introducing the resulting views to the management and as well as to the researchers and system engineers. Moreover it is a first step in the definition of a methodology for technology assessment and insertion for DISN. Currently, DISA is working on various Advance Technology Demonstrations of Asynchronous Transfer Mode (ATM) based network for achieving this capability for DISN.

5.0 References

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